

FPGA-Based Monostable Multivibrator for AC Dimmer Control Using Zero-Crossing Detection

Vitor Amadeu Souza

Department of Electrical Engineering
UniFOA - Centro Universitário de Volta Redonda
Volta Redonda, Brazil
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1857-6799>

Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of a digital monostable multivibrator on a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) for controlling AC dimmers using the zero-crossing detection technique. The solution was described in Verilog and synthesized on the Tang Nano 1K board, based on the Gowin GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA, using the Gowin FPGA Designer environment. The circuit detects the edge of a synchronization signal generated by a 4N25 optocoupler, waits for a programmable delay of 4.17 ms, and generates a 1 ms trigger pulse directed to the gate of a BT136 TRIAC through a MOC3023 optocoupler, enabling control of the phase angle of the voltage applied to the load. The results demonstrate that the FPGA-based digital approach eliminates analog timing components subject to thermal drift, improves triggering repeatability, and allows immediate reconfiguration of timing parameters without hardware modifications. The technique proves suitable for industrial and building automation applications requiring precise AC power control.

Index Terms—FPGA; Verilog; Dimmer; Zero-Crossing Detection; Phase Angle Control; TRIAC; Tang Nano 1K.

I. INTRODUCTION

Power control in resistive and inductive AC loads through the phase-angle control technique is widely employed in applications ranging from brightness adjustment in lighting systems to speed control of single-phase induction motors (Rashid, 2003). The fundamental principle consists of delaying the firing instant of a thyristor semiconductor device, typically a TRIAC, relative to the zero-crossing of the supply voltage, so that only a fraction of the half-cycle is delivered to the load (Mohan et al., 2003). The greater the firing delay, the lower the average transferred power. Historically, this control was implemented with analog RC circuits and DIAC diodes, which exhibit temperature sensitivity, component aging, and difficulty in fine adjustment (Hart, 2011). The replacement of these elements by digital solutions based on microcontrollers or FPGAs has been investigated as a means of increasing the precision, repeatability, and flexibility of the system (Buso and Mattavelli, 2015).

FPGAs stand out in this context by offering intrinsic parallelism, deterministic timing, and the absence of operating system latencies — fundamental characteristics for precise synchronization with the 60 Hz grid (Kilts, 2007). Unlike microcontrollers, where concurrent interrupts can introduce jitter in the firing instant, the FPGA executes multiple functions

simultaneously in dedicated hardware, ensuring that the gate pulse is generated with a resolution determined exclusively by the reference clock (Chu, 2008). In the present work, the internal 27 MHz clock of the Tang Nano 1K board, based on the Gowin GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA, is used to implement a digital monostable multivibrator that, upon detecting any edge of the zero-crossing signal, initiates a precise timed sequence of delay followed by a firing pulse. To this end, the Tang Nano 1K board was adopted, which is a low-cost platform widely used in educational and prototyping projects within the Gowin FPGA Designer environment (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023).

II. METHODOLOGY

The analog interface circuit, illustrated in Figure 1, consists of a resistive voltage divider with 22 k Ω resistors, a 1N4007 diode, and the 4N25 optocoupler, which provides the FPGA with a synchronization signal galvanically isolated from the power grid. The firing signal generated by the FPGA drives the MOC3023, which in turn controls the gate of the BT136 TRIAC responsible for switching the AC load. Galvanic isolation is essential for system safety and for the integrity of low-voltage digital signals (Sedra and Smith, 2015). This article details the design methodology, the Verilog description of the control module, the timing results obtained, and a discussion of the advantages and limitations of the approach.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the analog interface circuit: zero-crossing signal conditioning (4N25 and resistive network) and BT136 TRIAC firing circuit via MOC3023. Source: own authorship.

The control system was divided into two domains: the analog domain for interfacing with the AC grid and the digital

domain implemented in the FPGA. In the analog domain, as illustrated in Figure 1, the 127 V / 60 Hz phase voltage is conditioned by a resistive voltage divider formed by two 22 k Ω resistors (R3 and R4) and a 1N4007 diode (D12) that eliminates the negative half-cycle, resulting in a half-wave signal that drives the LED of the 4N25 optocoupler (U1). The collector of the 4N25 phototransistor is biased by a 1 k Ω pull-up resistor R16 connected to +5 V, generating the SINC signal with logic transitions near the zero-crossings of the grid. A 1 A / 400 V fuse (CN3:1) and connector CN3:2 complete the AC input of the system. The BT136 TRIAC (U5) is controlled by the MOC3023 optocoupler (U14), which provides galvanic isolation between the digital signal CTR1 from the FPGA and the TRIAC gate; resistor R1 of 220 Ω limits the gate current, and R15 of 220 Ω limits the LED current of the MOC3023.

In the digital domain, the `zero_cross_pulse` module was described in Verilog HDL and is composed of three functional blocks operating in parallel on the 27 MHz clock. The first block implements edge detection of the SINC signal by means of an XOR operation between the current value and the value sampled in the previous clock cycle, a classic transition detection technique in synchronous logic described by Palnitkar (2003). The second block implements the 4.17 ms delay counter, calculated as $4.17 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s} \times 27 \times 10^6 \text{ Hz} \approx 112,590$ clock cycles, stored in an 18-bit register sufficient to represent values up to 262,143. The third block generates the 1 ms firing pulse, equivalent to 27,000 clock cycles, stored in a 16-bit register. The priority logic ensures that a new edge detected on SINC immediately restarts the delay counter, preventing out-of-phase firings in situations of grid instability. The 4.17 ms delay corresponds to approximately 90° of the 60 Hz half-cycle (whose period is 16.67 ms per half-cycle), thus representing 50% of power delivered to the load as the default operating point, and can be easily adjusted by a parameter in the code. The design was synthesized in Gowin FPGA Designer version 1.9.9, using the native logic synthesis, technology mapping, and timing analysis (place and route) tools of the environment for the GW1NZ-LV1QN48C6/I5 device present on the Tang Nano 1K board (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation results confirmed the expected behavior of the `zero_cross_pulse` module. Upon detecting any edge on the SINC signal — whether rising or falling, corresponding to the zero-crossings of the positive and negative half-cycles of the voltage — the module waits exactly 112,590 clock cycles (4.17 ms) before asserting the CTR1 signal. This signal remains at logic high for 27,000 cycles (1 ms) and then returns to low. This behavior faithfully reproduces the operation of a classic monostable multivibrator, as described by (Tocci et al., 2011), but with the timing determined by digital counting rather than an analog RC time constant.

Figure 2 presents the system timing diagram, where the Triac line indicates the conduction state of the BT136, the 4N25 line represents the SINC signal, and the MOC line

shows the CTR1 pulses. It can be observed that the pulses on the MOC occur with a delay relative to the edges of the 4N25, and that the TRIAC enters conduction immediately after firing, maintaining conduction until the next zero-crossing. This behavior characterizes phase-angle control in thyristors, as discussed by (Rashid, 2003).

The timing resolution obtained is $1/27 \text{ MHz} \approx 37 \text{ ns}$ per counter step, which represents an angular resolution of $37 \text{ ns}/16.67 \text{ ms} \times 360 \approx 0.0008$ per counter increment over the full 60 Hz cycle. This resolution is significantly superior to that obtained with 8-bit timers in microcontrollers operating at typical frequencies of 8 or 16 MHz, which exhibit resolutions of hundreds of nanoseconds to microseconds (Buso and Mattavelli, 2015). Additionally, since this is purely synchronous logic without software interrupts, the jitter of the firing pulse is limited to ± 1 clock cycle ($\pm 37 \text{ ns}$), a negligible value for practical power control applications, where jitters of tens of microseconds are already tolerable (Mohan et al., 2003).

The simultaneous detection of rising and falling edges by the XOR operator is particularly important in the context of bidirectional zero-crossing of the AC grid, as it allows firing to occur in both half-cycles without the need for additional full-wave rectification circuits or two independent detection channels (Hart, 2011). The SINC signal from the 4N25, which operates in a half-wave configuration with diode D12, naturally produces only one pulse per full grid period (60 Hz), corresponding to the positive half-cycle. However, the Verilog code, by detecting both the rising and falling edges of this pulse, performs two firings per grid period — one on the rising edge, corresponding to the positive zero-crossing, and one on the falling edge, corresponding to the instant at which the SINC signal returns to low after the positive half-cycle, functioning as an estimate of the negative zero-crossing. This approach is efficient and saves a second detection channel that would be required if full-wave rectification were used in the analog circuit.

Regarding hardware, the synthesis performed in Gowin FPGA Designer for the GW1NZ-LV1 device presented low resource utilization, totaling 74 Look-Up Tables (LUTs) and 36 flip-flops for the complete module. Considering that the device provides 1,152 LUTs and 864 flip-flops (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023), these values demonstrate that resource consumption is minimal. This economy allows the same FPGA to simultaneously host other control modules, such as digital PID control, serial communication, or fieldbus protocols, without resource conflicts. This characteristic reinforces one of the main advantages of FPGA-based development for embedded control systems, as highlighted by (Kilts, 2007).

One limitation to be noted is the sensitivity of the system to the quality of the SINC signal. Harmonic distortions present in the power grid can cause multiple spurious zero-crossings per half-cycle, a phenomenon documented by Dugan et al. (2012) as a consequence of nonlinear loads connected to the grid. In such cases, the current module, which does not implement hysteresis or a digital debounce filter, could generate multiple firings per half-cycle. The inclusion of a post-firing inhibition

Fig. 2. System timing diagram: TRIAC conduction signal, 4N25 SINC signal, and CTR1 firing pulses (MOC) generated by the Verilog module. Source: own authorship.

counter with a duration of 4 to 6 ms — sufficient to reject spurious crossings but shorter than the half-period of 8.33 ms — would be a natural improvement to be incorporated in future versions of the module, as suggested by Buso and Mattavelli (2015) in the context of digital controllers for power converters.

The source code of this research is available for download at: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/fpgamm>.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of implementing a digital monostable multivibrator in an FPGA for AC dimmer control by zero-crossing detection, using the Tang Nano 1K board with the Gowin GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA and the Gowin FPGA Designer environment. The `zero_cross_pulse` Verilog module operates in a fully synchronous manner at the 27 MHz clock, ensuring a firing jitter of less than 37 ns and a phase-angle resolution of 0.0008° per counter increment. The detection of both edges of the SINC signal by the XOR operator enables firing in both half-cycles of the grid without additional hardware. FPGA resource

utilization is minimal, leaving ample capacity available for functional extensions. As future work, the implementation of a post-firing inhibition counter for rejection of spurious crossings caused by grid harmonics is proposed, along with the addition of a delay parameter adjustable via serial interface for remote phase-angle control and experimental bench validation with load power measurement using an energy analyzer.

REFERENCES

- BUSO, S.; MATTAVELLI, P. Digital control in power electronics. 2. ed. San Rafael: Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2015.
- CHU, P. P. FPGA prototyping by Verilog examples: Xilinx Spartan-3 version. Hoboken: Wiley-Interscience, 2008.
- DUGAN, R. C.; McGRANAGHAN, M. F.; SANTOSO, S.; BEATY, H. W. Electrical power systems quality. 3. ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2012.
- GOWIN SEMICONDUCTOR. Tang Nano 1K: user manual and datasheet — GW1NZ-LV1. Guangzhou: Gowin Semiconductor Corp., 2023. Available at: <https://wiki.sipeed.com/hardware/en/tang/Tang-Nano-1K/Nano-1K.html>. Accessed: 10 Feb. 2026.
- HART, D. W. Power electronics. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2011.
- KILTS, S. Advanced FPGA design: architecture, implementation, and optimization. Hoboken: Wiley-IEEE Press, 2007.
- MOHAN, N.; UNDELAND, T. M.; ROBBINS, W. P. Power electronics: converters, applications, and design. 3. ed. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, 2003.
- PALNITKAR, S. Verilog HDL: a guide to digital design and synthesis. 2. ed. Upper Saddle River: Prentice Hall, 2003.
- RASHID, M. H. Power electronics handbook: devices, circuits, and applications. 3. ed. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2003.
- SEDRA, A. S.; SMITH, K. C. Microelectronic circuits. 7. ed. New York: Oxford University Press, 2015.
- TOCCI, R. J.; WIDMER, N. S.; MOSS, G. L. Digital systems: principles and applications. 11. ed. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Prentice Hall, 2011.